

X-Ray diffraction studies of Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes with 2-[2'-hydroxysalicylidene-5'-(2''-thiazolylazo)]phenol

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The metal complexes of the type [ML(H₂O)₂]₂ (where M = Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} and H₂L = 2-[2'-hydroxysalicylidene-5'-(2''-thiazolylazo)]phenol) have been synthesized and subjected to the X-ray diffractometry to elucidate structural information. The structure of the complexes are found to be tetragonal belonging to non-primitive system. The strain broadening effects are also examined and discussed.

Metal complexes with potentially tridentate and tetradentate ligands have evoked much interest in coordination chemistry¹. These ligands have tendency to form dimeric or polymeric complexes with divalent metal ion resulting into the formation of compounds having distinguishable magnetic and spectral properties². In continuation of our earlier work³, the synthesis and X-ray diffraction studies of Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes with 2-[2'-hydroxysalicylidene-5'-(2''-thiazolylazo)]phenol (H₂L) were undertaken in the present investigation.

Results and discussion

The analytical data of Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes suggest their general formula [M(L)(H₂O)₂]₂ with their mo-

lecular formula Ni₂C₃₂H₂₈N₈O₈S₂, Cu₂C₃₂H₂₈N₈O₈S₂ and Zn₂C₃₂H₂₈N₈O₈S₂ respectively, where H₂L = 2-[2'-hydroxysalicylidene-5'-(2''-thiazolylazo)]phenol. The diffractogram of Ni^{II} complex records thirteen reflections between 10 and 80° (2θ) with maxima at 2θ = 44.64° corresponding to value of *d* = 2.028 Å (Table 1). The diffratogram of Cu^{II} complex consists of thirteen reflections with maxima at 2θ = 44.63° corresponding to value of *d* = 2.029 Å (Table 2), where Zn^{II} complex records seven reflections between 10 and 80° (2θ) with maximum reflection at 2θ = 44.62° corresponding to value of *d* = 2.029 Å (Table 3) between 10 and 80°. The programme was modified in such a way that a good fit could be obtained between observed and calculated *d* and *Q* values and having symmetry constraints. The

Table 1. XRD data of [NiL.(H₂O)₂]₂

Peak no.	2θ degree	<i>d</i> _{obs} Å	<i>d</i> _{cal} Å	<i>Q</i> _{obs}	<i>Q</i> _{cal}	<i>hkl</i>	<i>R</i> <i>I</i> (%)	σ(<i>Q</i>)x 10 ⁻⁴
1	10.88	8.121	8.138	0.0152	0.0151	0 2 1	17.4	1.00
2	12.16	7.272	7.293	0.0189	0.0188	0 0 2	61.0	2.00
3	13.00	6.804	6.836	0.0216	0.0214	0 1 2	12.8	2.00
4	15.21	5.818	5.852	0.0295	0.0292	0 2 2	7.1	2.00
5	20.85	4.256	4.252	0.0552	0.0553	1 2 3	10.3	3.00
6	23.53	3.777	3.788	0.0701	0.0697	3 4 1	15.2	3.00
7	24.40	3.645	3.647	0.0753	0.0752	0 0 4	18.3	3.00
8	26.50	3.361	3.363	0.0885	0.0884	3 5 0	5.8	3.00
9	27.61	3.228	3.227	0.0960	0.0960	2 2 4	10.3	3.00
10	38.46	2.338	2.341	0.1828	0.1825	3 4 5	32.1	5.00
11	44.64	2.028	2.027	0.2431	0.2433	1 2 7	100.0	5.00
12	64.97	1.434	1.436	0.4862	0.4847	2 6 9	15.7	7.00
13	78.16	1.221	1.217	0.6708	0.6752	7 8 9	12.5	7.00

Table 2. XRD data of [CuL.(H₂O)₂]₂

Peak no.	2θ degree	<i>d</i> _{obs} Å	<i>d</i> _{cal} Å	<i>Q</i> _{obs}	<i>Q</i> _{cal}	<i>hkl</i>	<i>RI</i> (%)	σ(<i>Q</i>) _x 10 ⁻⁴
1	11.17	7.913	7.906	0.0159	0.0160	0 2 1	97.7	1.00
2	18.74	4.731	4.725	0.0447	0.0448	0 4 0	54.6	2.00
3	19.59	4.528	4.527	0.0488	0.0488	1 1 3	22.8	2.00
4	23.66	3.757	3.748	0.0709	0.0712	3 1 3	40.5	3.00
5	25.12	3.541	3.544	0.0797	0.0796	3 2 3	18.6	3.00
6	27.34	3.259	3.255	0.0942	0.0944	4 4 1	33.6	3.00
7	31.32	2.854	2.884	0.1228	0.1228	0 1 5	8.7	4.00
8	38.44	2.340	2.336	0.1826	0.1832	5 5 3	54.6	5.00
9	44.63	2.029	2.029	0.2430	0.2428	0 5 6	100.0	5.00
10	48.24	1.885	1.886	0.2815	0.2812	6 7 3	80.7	5.00
11	59.36	1.555	1.554	0.4133	0.4140	0 3 9	40.7	6.00
12	64.92	1.435	1.434	0.4855	0.4864	0 8 8	22.8	7.00
13	78.09	1.223	1.223	0.6688	0.6688	6 8 9	15.8	7.00

Table 3. XRD data of [ZnL.(H₂O)₂]₂

Peak no.	2θ degree	<i>d</i> _{obs} Å	<i>d</i> _{cal} Å	<i>Q</i> _{obs}	<i>Q</i> _{cal}	<i>hkl</i>	<i>RI</i> (%)	σ(<i>Q</i>) _x 10 ⁻⁴
1	33.09	2.705	2.717	0.1367	0.1355	1 2 5	1.8	4.00
2	38.41	2.342	2.341	0.1824	0.1824	2 6 4	28.3	5.00
3	44.62	2.029	2.030	0.2429	0.2427	0 1 7	100.0	5.00
4	44.73	2.024	2.024	0.2441	0.2440	1 5 6	77.5	5.00
5	58.84	1.568	1.567	0.4067	0.4072	0 6 8	1.9	6.00
6	65.03	1.432	1.435	0.4870	0.4853	3 5 9	16.8	7.00
7	77.21	1.234	1.233	0.8104	0.8110	6 8 9	8.6	7.00

method also yielded *hkl* (miller indices) values. The relative intensities corresponding to the prominent peaks have been measured.

The indexing of diffractogram of Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes are nearly identical. Based on this it can be proposed that these compounds belong to same structural class. A comparison of value of *d* and *Q* for the Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes reveals that, there is good agreement between the calculated and observed value of *d* and *Q* on the basis of assumption of tetragonal structure⁴. The small differences in the observed *d* spacing can be attributed to difference in unit cell dimensions. The differences in the intensities may be due to grinding and packing effects combined with increase in scattering power on going from nickel to zinc. The structure of Ni^{II} complex yields values for lattice constant *a* = *b* = 19.612 Å, *c* = 14.586 Å and unit cell volume *V* = 5610.22 Å³. The structure of Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes yields values for lattice constant and unit cell volume *a* = *b* = 18.898 Å, *c* = 14.434 Å, *V* = 5154.87 Å³ and *a* = *b* = 19.612 Å, *c* = 14.286 Å, *V* = 5494.83 Å³ respectively. In

conjunction with these evaluated cell parameters, the conditions⁵ such as *a* = *b* ≠ *c* and of α = β = γ = 90° required for the samples to be tetragonal were tested and found to be satisfactory. Hence it is concluded that the structure of the complexes under study belong to tetragonal crystal system.

The experimental density of the complexes under study were determined by using specific gravity method, which further enabled to calculate the volume of unit cell. By using this value of density, molecular weight of the complexes, Avogadro's number and volume of unit cell, the numbers of molecules (*n*) per unit cell were calculated by using equation $\rho = nm/NV$ and was found to be 4. With this number theoretical density was fixed. The other parameters such as pore fraction; thickness of particle were then calculated. All these parameters are entered in Table 4. The particle size of the complexes were determined by using equation $t = 0.9 \lambda / B \cos \theta$, where λ is wavelength of X-ray radiation in Å, *B* is the half angular width in radians and θ is Bragg's diffraction angle. These parameters can distinguish between natural particle size and particle size due to broadening ef-

Table 4. X-Ray parameters of Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes with 2-[2'-hydroxysalicylidene-5'-(2''-thiazolylazo)]phenol

Sl. no.	Parameters	[NiL.(H ₂ O) ₂] ₂	[CuL.(H ₂ O) ₂] ₂	[ZnL.(H ₂ O) ₂] ₂
1.	Structure	Tetragonal	Tetragonal	Tetragonal
2.	Lattice parameters	$a = b = 19.612 \text{ \AA}$ $c = 14.586 \text{ \AA}$	$a = b = 18.898 \text{ \AA}$ $c = 14.434 \text{ \AA}$	$a = b = 19.612 \text{ \AA}$ $c = 14.286 \text{ \AA}$
3.	Volume of unit cell (V)	5610.22 \AA^3	5154.87 \AA^3	5494.83 \AA^3
4.	Density (ρ)			
	Experimental	0.99 g cm^{-3}	1.09 g cm^{-3}	1.02 g cm^{-3}
	Theoretical	0.96 g cm^{-3}	1.03 g cm^{-3}	0.99 g cm^{-3}
5.	Number of molecules (n)/unit cell	4	4	4
6.	Pore fraction (%)	17.52	14.58	10.45
7.	Thickness of particle	233.17 \AA	221.00 \AA	271.08 \AA

fect. This was done by calculating full width at half maximum (B) corresponding to its Bragg's θ and thereby computing \cos and \sin values.

A plot of $B \cos\theta$ versus $\sin \theta$ was found to be straight line, parallel to X-axis indicating absence of any strains caused by inhomogeneous lattice distortions and compositional fluctuations. Hence, present samples seems to be homogeneous with respect to the particle size distribution.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of A.R. grade. The compound 2-[2'-hydroxysalicylidene-5'-(2''-thiazolylazo)]phenol (H_2L) was prepared by the reported method⁶. The metal complexes of Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} were prepared by refluxing 15 ml of an ethanolic solution of the appropriate metal(II) chloride (0.01 mol) with 30 ml of an ethanolic solution of H_2L (3.243 g, 0.01 mol) for one hour. After cooling, the pH of the mixture was raised to 7.5 by the addition of a dilute alcoholic ammonia solution. The resultant solid was filtered, washed with ethanol and dried in air.

The elemental analysis were carried out in microanalytical laboratory (University of Pune). The XRD spectra were recorded on Philips PW 3710 diffractometer attached to a digitized computer alongwith graphical assembly using CuK_{α} radiation source. The X-ray tube was operated at 25 kV/20 mA. The samples were scanned in the 2θ range from 10 to 80° at a scanning speed of 2θ /min.

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